
Research

Identifying Key Factors for Traffic Safety: A Case Study of Driver Behavior in Peshawar, Pakistan

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Abstract: Driver behavior significantly impacts road safety, particularly in developing countries like Peshawar, Pakistan, where comprehensive studies are lacking. This research addresses this gap by examining driver behaviors related to traffic safety in Peshawar. Utilizing a Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ) administered through Google Forms, data was collected from 120 respondents. This study employs a Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) method to evaluate ranking criteria and weight factors, considering the unique uncertainties of driving behavior. Results highlight violations as the primary concern, followed by errors and lapses, with subcategories delineated through pairwise comparisons, shedding light on prevalent issues like reckless driving and errors in judgment. Common behaviors such as overtaking slow drivers and abrupt lane changes were identified. Failure to use seat belts, underestimating vehicle speeds, and using mobile devices while driving were also commonly reported. The study's diverse sample, obtained through document-based questionnaires distributed via email to individuals aged 18 and above, including university students, provided insights into driving habits. The majority of respondents held valid driver's licenses, with an average weekly travel distance of 208.5 km reported. These findings offer policymakers valuable insights for targeted interventions aimed at improving traffic safety in Peshawar and serve as a benchmark for similar studies in other developing countries.

Keywords: Traffic Safety, Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ), Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Violations, Errors, Lapses, Road Safety.

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Introduction

Globally, over 1.35 million people die in traffic accidents yearly by W.H.O. [1], with a significant societal cost of about 2% of GDP in European countries. In 2012, road accidents claimed 27,700 lives in the EU27, with Italy having a higher fatality rate compared to other European nations (ACI, 2013). Pakistan, a low-middle-income country, faces substantial road accident challenges, with an average of 15 daily fatalities [2]. In 2017, Punjab reported 9,648 road accident deaths, likely underestimated [3,4].

Furthermore, road accidents cost the nation approximately 6.48 million USD annually (1 USD = 285.93 PKR) [5]. They rank as the second leading cause of disability, fifth in total healthy life years lost, and eleventh in premature mortality in Pakistan [6]. These alarming statistics underscore the urgent need for enhanced road safety efforts, motivating the

current study. Globally, researchers have focused on two main areas: crash frequency and injury severity. Lord & Mannering [7] explored crash frequency data, proposing alternative approaches and discussing analysis limitations. Similarly, the researcher examined crash severity data, assessing features, methodologies, and constraints [8,9]. Wang et al. categorized collision causes into infrastructural, human, and vehicle factors. Given the gravity of the issue, further research is vital to mitigate traffic accidents [10]. Road and traffic elements, including geometry, surface conditions, traffic flow, speed, and weather, constitute one group of collision causes. Human factors, such as driver attitude, history, health, and personality traits, play a significant role as well.

In a world of evolving vehicles and roads, remarkable advancements have propelled safety to unprecedented levels. The research underscores the crucial role of human behavior in preventing accidents [11]. Despite this recognition, there's a significant gap in understanding how human factors contribute to unsafe driving and crashes. Driver error accounts for 70% to 80% of global road crashes, with up to 96% attributed, at least partially, to mistakes [12]. Improving human factors influencing driving behaviors is essential for effective accident prevention and road safety enhancement. Scholars have noted the profound impact of a driver's perception of the road on behavior and performance, yet assessing safety perception remains challenging [10]. This study aims to uncover key variables influencing driver behavior in traffic accidents, focusing on violation and error, drawing on previous research and a preliminary survey. Despite few studies evaluating driver behaviors in Peshawar, Pakistan, a comprehensive analysis is crucial to fill this gap and understand cultural nuances. The study employs the Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process (FAHP) to rank driver behavior, providing a standardized framework for traffic safety management. Cultural and socioeconomic factors may influence how Pakistani drivers are evaluated, requiring careful consideration of the assessment criteria. By integrating FAHP, this research aims to develop a nuanced understanding of driver behavior in Peshawar, Pakistan, tailored to its unique cultural and social context.

The objectives of this study are as follows: Firstly, to conduct a driver behavior questionnaire focusing on factors contributing to road accidents and the socioeconomic profiles of drivers in Peshawar, Pakistan, aiming to comprehend the impact of driver behavior on traffic safety. Given the lack of comprehensive nationwide data on driver behavior, the study advocates for employing a driver behavior survey for data collection. Secondly, to utilize the fuzzy AHP for ranking the criteria of the most influential factors in road accidents, addressing the research gap in this area within the study region. The findings of this study can provide valuable insights for stakeholders and policymakers to devise effective strategies for managing driving behavior, particularly in low-income countries like Pakistan and other regions with similar demographic and social characteristics, such as India, Sri Lanka, Nepal, and Bangladesh.

Literature Review

The escalating frequency of road traffic accidents (RTAs) has inflicted significant harm on numerous countries, resulting in a substantial number of deaths and injuries. According to the World Economic Forum [13,14], the global vehicle population is predicted to double by 2040, exerting further strain on the transportation system. Projections from the World Health Organization (WHO) [14,15] suggest that by 2030, RTAs could rank as the seventh leading cause of fatalities. Vulnerable road users, such as bicyclists, motorcyclists, and pedestrians, bear the brunt of RTAs, accounting for over half (54%) of the total fatalities [13,14].

An RTA is defined as an incident involving at least one road vehicle that occurs on a public road and results in at least one person being injured or killed [16]. Leading causes of RTAs include speeding, driving under the influence (DUI), and distractions caused by cell phone use while driving. The WHO's 2015 estimates highlight the impact of RTA fatalities on different nations: developing nations reported 24.1 fatalities per 100,000 people, middle-income nations reported 18.4 fatalities per 100,000, and developed nations reported 9.2 fatalities per 100,000 [16]. This data underscores that lower- and middle-income nations contribute to more than double the fatalities compared to higher-income countries. An RTA occurs when two cars collide, causing bodily harm, property destruction, and even fatalities. This occurs whenever an automobile upon that highway, like a car, truck, bus, or motorbike, comes into contact with certain other cars,

people, wildlife/animals, road debris, or other topographical & architectural barriers [17]. Such incidents usually contain three factors: the operator/driver (human), its roadway automobile, as well as the traffic environment. Moreover, it was shown that human activities cause over 90% of such incidents, & such dangerous driving behavior had a significant part in these events [18]. Super speeder, drifting between and within road lanes, and going past red lights and stop signages are all examples of hazardous driver behavior which endangers both operators/drivers and other road users. Due to the importance of this sort of driving behavior, it's not shocking that huge volumes of research have concentrated on investigating the connection of this behavior with a variety of human aspects, particularly mental and social factors, and that variations in driving behavior are among the keys to road traffic safety assessments [19-21]. In 1990 were also inspired to create a research instrument, the Drivers-Behavior-Questionnaire (DBQ), to assess driving behavior and automobile users. [22]

Numerous studies consistently highlight that human factors stand as the primary contributors to significant casualties in traffic accidents. Consequently, the foremost focus of efforts to enhance road safety should be addressing these human-related issues [23]. Reports indicate that human factors account for the majority of traffic accidents, either as the sole cause or as the primary factor [24-26]. A previous study emphasized that driving behavior, driver risk perception, and experience are pivotal elements in determining road safety [27]. Additionally, notable regional variations exist in driving habits and risk perception [28, 29].

Human factors are central to the majority of accidents [30, 31]. Driver abilities and driving style are two critical facets of human factors when it comes to driving. While driving style is influenced by motivations, beliefs, and personality traits, driving abilities are rooted in motor skills and information processing [32]. In reality, driving styles and abilities intersect to influence collision risk, safety factor usage, failure frequency, and recovery from errors [33-36]. Research on driving unusually emerges as a significant paradigm shift towards a comprehensive understanding of daily driving behaviors. The DBQ conceptualized on a theoretical framework of aberrant behaviors [37], unveiled two distinct categories of driver behavior errors and violations, encompassing three variables (intentional violation, hazardous errors, and 'silly' errors). Subsequent studies confirmed the three-factor structure of the DBQ, underscoring its temporal consistency [38].

The escalating number of vehicles on roads raises concerns about traffic flow and road safety. The enhancement of road guards and the reduction of accidents are now paramount priorities for authorities worldwide. Distracted driving stands as a primary cause of accidents, stemming from drivers' lack of focus. Despite the understanding that driving necessitates unwavering attention to the road and surrounding vehicles, drivers often succumb to distractions like phone calls, glancing at signs, conversations, eating, interacting with passengers, and adjusting the radio. Moreover, distraction can result from stressful events, leading to erratic driver behavior [39].

A significant portion of road accidents is attributed to poor driving practices. The online monitoring of drivers' unusual driving patterns holds the potential to prevent collisions. Recent attention has been directed towards detecting aberrant driving behaviors based on sensor data integrated into commonly used smartphones. However, despite advancements in identifying driving behavior, existing studies still struggle to attain high recognition accuracy and exhibit limited resilience [40].

Stress-related distractions can also lead to erratic driving behavior. The prevalence of stress-inducing factors like impaired driving, traffic congestion, work overload, personal challenges, and more has contributed to the rise of stress-related diversions. Such diversions can manifest as speeding, swerving, aggressive braking, and other abnormal behaviors. Furthermore, a driver's emotional and physiological state significantly influences their driving behavior, potentially leading to drowsy driving when they are unwell or excessively fatigued [39]. According to the latest PakWheels.com Car Industry Survey, which gathered responses from over 11,000 individuals, 24% of the participants

admitted to not having a driver's license. However, within this non-licensed segment, 41% were juveniles, primarily under the age of 21, as illustrated in Figure 1 [41].

Figure 1 Car driver without driver's license with age

Another study conducted, as the population of individuals aged 65 and above grows in the US, concerns have emerged about the impact of this demographic shift on road safety [42]. By 2030, it is projected that drivers aged 65 and older will constitute one-fifth of all drivers [43]. The prevalence of medical impairments, including cognitive deficits, increases with age, as does vulnerability to injury in accidents or driving errors that contribute to collisions [43–46]. Most concerns regarding elderly drivers revolve around potential risks to other road users, especially following widely publicized accidents where elderly drivers were deemed responsible [47]. This has prompted various jurisdictions to implement road tests or more frequent license renewals for drivers beyond a certain age, in addition to exploring viable methods for identifying potentially hazardous older drivers [48-49].

It remains uncertain whether aged drivers pose a significant risk not only to themselves but also to other vehicular traffic. On average, aged drivers cover fewer miles per year, which diminishes the collision involvement risk per driver [50], yet they experience a notable increase in fatality involvement per mile [51]. Studies suggest that frailty is a key factor contributing to higher fatality rates per mile among elderly drivers, with a greater impact on other drivers becoming evident around the age of seventy-five [51]. Another study found a slightly higher risk of both fatalities and hospitalizations per mile among occupants of other vehicles involved in two-car crashes in Wisconsin, where one of the drivers was 75 years or older [52]. Other research also indicated that senior drivers pose increased hazards per mile to other road users [53]. Furthermore, a study observed that elderly drivers were involved in fewer pedestrian fatalities compared to younger and middle-aged drivers. However, while elderly drivers had fewer pedestrian fatalities per licensed driver, they had more pedestrian fatalities per unit of traffic. The study concluded that renewing a license for an eighty-year-old driver resulted in less harm to others on the road than renewing a license for a forty-year-old driver, due to the lower travel distances among the elderly drivers [54].

This literature review examines studies and methods analyzing driver behavior to enhance road safety, which is crucial for efficient transportation. Driver behavior, influenced by factors like speeding and traffic violations, significantly impacts accident likelihood and carries social, financial, and economic repercussions [55,56]. Over two decades, numerous studies have focused on creating, modifying, and evaluating methods for assessing driver behavior. Reason et al. (1990) introduced a 50-item self-report driver behavior questionnaire (DBQ), widely used since then [57]. The DBQ assesses violations, errors, and lapses, which account for a significant portion of the variance in driver behavior. Human factors play a central role in accidents, with driver abilities and driving style influencing collision risk and safety measures [58-

60]. The DBQ's three- or four-factor structure, including errors, lapses, aggressive, and ordinary violations, has been replicated in studies worldwide, demonstrating cross-cultural reliability [61,62]. However, some studies identified additional factors, varying the number of DBQ variables [63].

In literature, methodologies for ranking and weighting criteria in Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ) studies often involve Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) techniques like Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Fuzzy AHP. To address uncertainty and inconsistency, researchers have employed various techniques alongside AHP, such as interconnections, frequency ratio, sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, interval calculations, and modified AHP. Additionally, scholars have integrated fuzzy theory with AHP for handling ambiguity in comparisons, offering enhanced precision and accuracy, particularly in the realm of human thought and behavior.

In summary, various methods have been employed to analyze the Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ). However, these studies face limitations, particularly concerning sample size and questionnaire scope. For instance, a previous study comparing driver behavior across multiple countries had a small sample size (70 participants per country) and a limited set of questionnaire questions. To overcome these limitations, the current study focuses on a single-country level, specifically, the city of Peshawar in Pakistan. Peshawar was chosen due to its unique cultural and social norms, making it an intriguing locale for research. The questionnaire has been refined based on a comprehensive literature review, with a specific emphasis on increasing participant numbers and expanding the question set to comprehensively capture driver behaviors related to traffic safety. This study addresses these gaps by employing the fuzzy AHP to rank criteria, highlighting influential factors contributing to traffic accidents. This approach provides valuable insights for decision-makers and stakeholders in developing effective driver behavior regulations and programs.

Methodology

This research is dedicated to exploring the factors influencing traffic safety through an in-depth examination of driver behavior. The conceptual framework depicting this investigation is illustrated in Figure 2. To achieve this objective, the study employs a structured approach, which involves the utilization of various methodologies.

- Initially, the study identifies the pertinent criteria, referred to as the Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ), aimed at evaluating driver behavior.
- Subsequently, hierarchical levels of decision-making are established to comprehend the influence of these criteria on driver behavior.
- Further analysis of the criteria and their impact on driver behavior is conducted using a specific methodology known as FAHP.

Figure 2 Workflow chart

Comprehensive Data Collection

This study employed a thorough approach to gather information on drivers by utilizing multiple methods to reach a diverse sample. Firstly, a document-based questionnaire was distributed via email to over 500 randomly selected individuals aged 18 and above. Recognizing the potential bias towards older participants in this method, additional data on younger drivers was collected by surveying university students from various institutions in Peshawar. This multi-pronged approach ensured a more representative sample, capturing insights from both the general population and the younger demographic. The study garnered a response rate of 25%, indicating a significant level of engagement from the participants. Among the respondents, approximately one-third were university students, while the majority comprised professionals such as engineers, doctors, and businessmen. This diversity in the sample population enriches the study's findings by providing insights from individuals with different backgrounds and lifestyles.

It is noteworthy that a substantial proportion of participants (65%) reported holding valid driver's licenses, indicating a strong representation of experienced drivers in the sample. However, the inclusion of individuals without driver's licenses also offers valuable perspectives on factors influencing road safety beyond direct driving experience. The age and gender distribution of the sample further reflect the diversity within the participant pool. The majority of drivers fell within the age range of 20 to 30, indicating a focus on younger adults who are likely to be active drivers. Additionally, the inclusion of women, who accounted for nearly one-quarter of the respondents, ensures gender representation in the study, allowing for gender-specific insights into driver behavior and attitudes towards road safety. Overall, this comprehensive approach to data collection provides a robust foundation for the study's analysis and findings. By incorporating perspectives from a wide range of participants, the study aims to offer nuanced insights into driver behavior and factors influencing road safety in Peshawar, Pakistan.

Driver Behavior Criteria

The study employed a Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to compare and evaluate the Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ) across various traffic cultures, utilizing well-established major driver behavior characteristics developed within the AHP framework [64]. These standards for driving behavior significantly influence traffic safety and are deemed crucial for ensuring the safety of other road users. According to Evans [65], driving behavior is undeniably the most critical factor affecting overall traffic safety.

To comprehensively examine each criterion, the driving behavior criteria were established for the research using a three-level hierarchical structure, abbreviated alphabetically. The primary driver behavior criteria, including violations and errors, constitute the first level. Figure 3 illustrates the breakdown of these primary driver behavior requirements into sub-criteria.

Figure 3 The hierarchical structure of the driver Behavior criteria

Fuzzy Analytical Hierarchy Process

Various FAHP applications and methodologies have been explored by different researchers. For instance, the initial use of triangular functions in fuzzy AHP research was documented by Van Laarhoven and Pedrycz [66]. Conversely, Cheng developed a unique level analysis technique to address the synthetic extent standards of fuzzy AHP in pairwise comparisons [67]. This method facilitates priority estimation in hierarchical structures by employing a comparison scale. The efficacy of FAHP modeling as a decision-making tool has been widely acknowledged by scholars [68].

In this study, the FAHP approach was utilized to determine the weights of driver behavior criteria and identify significant criteria impacting road safety. To enhance the accuracy of assessing factors influencing road safety, a fuzzy scale was employed in designing the driver behavior questionnaire. Fuzzy numbers derived from pairwise comparisons were used to categorize driver behavior and sub-criteria through a hierarchical approach (PCs). Survey data obtained from assessors representing specific traffic cultures were subjected to pairwise comparison, and global scores were derived.

A consistency test was conducted to validate the reliability of the driver behavior data. The researchers provided a concise overview of fuzzy hierarchical evaluation concepts, employing fuzzy logic to construct a questionnaire survey using triangular fuzzy numbers as a pairwise comparison scale [69].

In the realm of fuzzy logic, algebraic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, and reciprocation of two triangular fuzzy numbers $\check{A}_1 = (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ and $\check{A}_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2)$ can be expressed mathematically as follows:

Addition $\check{A}_1 + \check{A}_2 = (l_1, m_1, u_1) + (l_2, m_2, u_2) = (l_1 + l_2, m_1 + m_2, u_1 + u_2)$

Subtraction $\check{A}_1 - \check{A}_2 = (l_1, m_1, u_1) - (l_2, m_2, u_2) = (l_1 - l_2, m_1 - m_2, u_1 - u_2)$

Multiplications $\check{A}_1 \times \check{A}_2 = (l_1, m_1, u_1) \times (l_2, m_2, u_2) = (l_1 l_2, m_1 m_2, u_1 u_2)$

Division $\check{A}_1 \div \check{A}_2 = (l_1, m_1, u_1) / (l_2, m_2, u_2) = (l_1 / l_2, m_1 / m_2, u_1 / u_2)$

Reciprocal $\check{A}_1^{-1} = (l_1, m_1, u_1) = (\frac{1}{u_1}, \frac{1}{m_1}, \frac{1}{l_1})$

According to the method of extent analysis by Chang [69].

$$M_{gi}^1, M_{gi}^2, M_{gi}^3, \dots, M_{gi}^m \quad i = (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, n)$$

And all $M_{gi}^j (j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, m)$ are triangular fuzzy numbers given in Table 4.

The steps of Chang’s analysis can be described as follows:

Step 1. The fuzzy synthetic extent (S_i) value concerning i th criterion is defined as:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^m M_{gi}^j \times \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m M_{gi}^j \right]^{-1}$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^m M_{gi}^j = \left(\sum_{j=1}^m l_{ij}, \sum_{j=1}^m m_{ij}, \sum_{j=1}^m u_{ij} \right)$$

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m M_{gi}^j \right]^{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m u_{ij}}, \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m m_{ij}}, \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m l_{ij}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where l is the lower limit value, m is the most promising value and u is the upper limit value.

Step 2. The degree of Possibility of $S_2 = (l_2, m_2, u_2) \geq (l_1, m_1, u_1)$ can be defined as:

$$[V(S_2 \geq S_1) = \sup_{y \geq x} \left[\min \left(\mu_{s_1}(x), \mu_{s_2}(y) \right) \right]]$$

Table 1 TFN of linguistics comparison matrix

Linguistics variables	Assigned TFN
Equal	(1,1,1)
Very low	(1,2,3)
Medium	(2,3,4)
High	(3,4,5)
Very high	(4,5,6)
Excellent	(6,7,8)

Where x and y represent the values on an axis of the membership function of each criterion. This expression can be seen in equation (7) below:

$$V(S_2 \geq S_1) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } m_2 \geq m_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } l_1 \geq u_2 \\ \frac{l_1 - u_2}{(m_2 - u_2) - (m_1 - l_1)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where μ_d is the highest intersection point μ_{s_1} and μ_{s_2} , the graphical presentation can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4 The intersection of fuzzy numbers

To compare S_1 and S_2 , both $V(S_1 \geq S_2)$ and $V(S_2 \geq S_1)$ are required.

Step 3. The degree of possibility for a convex fuzzy number S to be greater than k convex fuzzy numbers $S_i = (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k)$ can be defined as:

$$V(S \geq S_1, S_2, \dots, S_k) = V[(S \geq S_1), (S \geq S_2), \dots, (S \geq S_k)]$$

$$= \min V(S \geq S_i), \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k \quad (8)$$

Assume that $d'(A_i) = \min V(S_i \geq S_k)$

For $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ $k \neq i$, the weight vectors are given in equation (9) as,

$$W' = (d'(A_1), d'(A_2), \dots, d'(A_m))^T \quad (9)$$

Step 4. Via normalization, the normalized weight vectors are given in equation (10) as,

$$W = (d(A_1), d(A_2), \dots, d(A_m))^T \quad (10)$$

In fuzzy logic, a non-fuzzy number is a precise numerical value, as opposed to a fuzzy number which represents a range of values with varying degrees of likelihood or membership.

The symbol "W" in the statement "And, W is the non-fuzzy number" refers to a specific numerical value that is not subject to fuzziness or uncertainty. It is a crisp value that can be used in mathematical operations without ambiguity.

Results

In this study, the fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology was employed to prioritize critical criteria in driver behavior, aiming to enhance traffic management in Peshawar, Pakistan. The investigation identified three primary criteria: violations, errors, and lapses. Violations were classified as the most severe category during the assessment of driver behavior. This category encompasses deliberate disregard for safety legislation or traffic laws, such as reckless driving or exceeding speed limits. Errors represent unintentional mistakes made by drivers, such as misjudging distances or failing to check blind spots, which can also lead to accidents and jeopardize lives. Lastly, lapses refer to unintentional errors such as forgetting to signal or failing to check mirrors, which contribute to unsafe driving conditions.

The fuzzy AHP method was utilized to analyze the pairwise comparisons between these criteria. Each criterion was evaluated based on its relative importance compared to the others. The weights obtained from the pairwise comparisons are presented in Table 2, indicating the relative significance of each criterion in influencing overall driver behavior.

Despite errors and lapses not posing an immediate threat like violations, they contribute to unsafe driving conditions and increase the likelihood of accidents. Therefore, it is crucial to consider all three factors when evaluating driver behavior and formulating policies to promote safe and responsible driving practices.

Table 2 Priority ranking of criteria for driver behavior

	ERROR	VIOLATIONS	Lapses	WEIGHT	RANK
ERROR	(1,1,1)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(2,3,4)	0.402	2
VIOLATIONS	(1,2,3)	(1,1,1)	(1,2,3)	0.550	1
Lapses	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(1,1,1)	0.048	3

In the study, the violations criterion was subdivided into two categories: aggressive violations and ordinary violations. Analysis revealed that "honking to indicate annoyance to others" emerged as the most prevalent form of aggressive driving behavior in Peshawar, Pakistan. This behavior poses a significant risk of conflicts and accidents on the road, as it can lead to aggressive confrontations between drivers and escalate tensions. Conversely, "chasing other drivers" was identified as the least common aggressive behavior shown in Table 3, indicating that while aggressive driving behaviors are present, extreme forms of aggression like chasing other drivers are relatively rare occurrences in Peshawar.

Furthermore, ordinary violations were classified into four criteria based on their frequency and impact on road safety. Among drivers in Peshawar, "overtaking slow drivers" was identified as the most prevalent ordinary violation. This behavior can lead to dangerous situations, especially on narrow roads or highways with limited visibility, increasing the risk of collisions. Following closely, "changing lanes at the last minute" was noted as another common ordinary violation. This behavior not only disrupts traffic flow but also heightens the likelihood of accidents, particularly if other drivers are not anticipating sudden lane changes. Additionally, "pulling out of junctions when other drivers have stopped" was identified as a prevalent ordinary violation. This action can lead to confusion and potentially cause rear-end collisions or obstruct the path of oncoming traffic, posing risks to both drivers and pedestrians. Lastly, "disregarding speed limits in residential areas" was highlighted as a common violation, as shown in Table 4. Excessive speeding in residential areas increases the risk of accidents, especially involving vulnerable road users such as children or elderly pedestrians. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of addressing both aggressive and ordinary violations in promoting road safety in Peshawar. Effective measures targeting these behaviors can help reduce the frequency of accidents and enhance the overall safety of road users in the city.

Table 3 Priority ranking of criteria for aggressive violations

	AV1	AV2	WEIGHT	RANK
AV1	(1,1,1)	(0.33,0.5,1)	0.50	1
AV2	(1,2,3)	(1,1,1)	0.50	2

Table 4 Priority ranking criteria for ordinary violations

	OV1	OV2	OV3	OV4	WEIGHT	RANK
OV1	(1,1,1)	(0.2,0.25,0.33)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	0.119674	4
OV2	(3,4,5)	(1,1,1)	(0.33,0.5)	(3,4,5)	0.350086	1
OV3	(1,2,3)	(1,2,3)	(1,1,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	0.239934	3
OV4	(2,3,4)	(0.2,0.25,0.33)	(2,3,4)	(1,1,1)	0.290306	2

In this study, errors in driver behavior were examined, focusing on mistakes stemming from a lack of knowledge, skills, or training. Four sub-criteria for errors were identified, shedding light on common lapses that contribute to unsafe driving practices. "Failure to use a seat belt during driving" emerged as the top-ranked error, indicating a concerning disregard for basic safety measures among drivers in Peshawar. This behavior poses a significant risk not only to the driver but also to passengers in the vehicle in the event of a collision. Ranked second was "Underestimating the speed of oncoming vehicles," highlighting a critical judgment error that can lead to dangerous situations, particularly during overtaking or when entering intersections. This error underscores the importance of accurate perception and assessment of traffic conditions to avoid accidents and collisions. Following closely, "Using a mobile device during driving" was identified as another prevalent error among drivers in Peshawar. This behavior poses a serious risk to road safety as it diverts the driver's attention from the road, increasing the likelihood of accidents due to distracted driving. Lastly, "Failure to notice pedestrians crossing" ranked fourth among identified errors, shown in Table 5. This highlights a lapse in attentiveness and awareness on the part of drivers, emphasizing the need for drivers to remain vigilant and attentive to their surroundings, particularly in areas with pedestrian activity. Addressing these hazardous behaviors is crucial for enhancing overall traffic safety in Peshawar. Effective interventions and educational campaigns targeting these specific errors can help raise awareness among drivers and encourage safer driving practices. By addressing these common errors, policymakers and traffic authorities can work towards creating a safer and more secure road environment for all road users in the city.

Table 5 Priority criteria of ranking for errors

	E1	E2	E3	E4	WEIGHT	RANK
E1	(1,1,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(2,3,4)	0.23149	2
E2	(2,3,4)	(1,1,1)	(2,3,4)	(1,2,3)	0.420554	1
E3	(1,2,3)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(1,1,1)	(0.33,0.5,1)	0.173978	3
E4	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(1,2,3)	(1,1,1)	0.173978	4

In this study, lapses in driver behavior, characterized as unintentional mistakes, were analyzed to understand their prevalence and impact on road safety in Peshawar. Despite being less severe than violations, lapses are still common among drivers and can contribute to traffic accidents. The analysis identified several sub-criteria of lapses, including instances such as "wrong Lane approach roundabout junction in the last position," "hit something while reversing," "using third gear while away from traffic light," and "switch one thing and on another."

Among these sub-criteria, the study found that "wrong Lane approach roundabout junction in the last position" was the most prevalent, indicating a common mistake made by drivers in navigating roundabouts. Following this, "hit something while reversing" ranked second, highlighting the frequency of accidents occurring during reversing maneuvers. Additionally, "switch one thing and on another" ranked third, indicating instances where drivers mistakenly activate or deactivate vehicle controls. Lastly, "using third gear while away from traffic light" ranked fourth, suggesting a less common but still noteworthy lapse in driver behavior, shown in Table 6.

These findings underscore the importance of addressing lapses in driver behavior to enhance road safety in Peshawar. By identifying common mistakes made by drivers, policymakers and stakeholders can implement targeted interventions and educational campaigns to mitigate these risks and promote safer driving practices.

In contrast to earlier research findings, the results of our study revealed notable disparities, which can be attributed to several key factors. Firstly, unlike prior studies that utilized shorter questionnaires and had limited participant numbers, our study employed an expanded questionnaire and included a larger sample size. Moreover, while previous research covered a broader geographic area with only 70 participants, our study focused exclusively on Peshawar, Pakistan. Another significant departure lies in our methodology for ranking driver behavior. While earlier studies relied on Kendall's agreement test, we employed fuzzy AHP, allowing us to account for the inherent uncertainties and imprecisions

in human behavior. This approach yielded a more thorough and precise assessment of driver behavior. These methodological and contextual differences contribute to the observed variations in study outcomes, underscoring the importance of tailoring the approach and considering specific factors when analyzing driver behavior in a particular location.

Table 6 Priority criteria of ranking for Lapses

	L1	L2	L3	L4	WEIGHT	RANK
L1	(1,1,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	0.039	1
L2	(2,3,4)	(1,1,1)	(0.33,0.5,1)	(2,3,4)	0.353	2
L3	(1,2,3)	(1,2,3)	(1,1,1)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	0.262	4
L4	(2,3,4)	(0.25,0.33,0.5)	(2,3,4)	(1,1,1)	0.347	3

Conclusions

The study provides valuable insights into the factors that contribute to driver behavior and improved traffic management in Peshawar. Fuzzy AHP is used to rank the driver behavior with pairwise comparison and sub-criteria subsequently. The study utilized fuzzy AHP to analyze driver behavior and derived significant results. The study identified three main criteria for assessing driver behavior was ranked: 1st violations, 2nd errors, and 3rd lapses. Violations involve intentional disregard for safety laws, such as careless driving or speeding. Errors are unintentional mistakes, like misjudging distances or neglecting blind spots. Lapses refer to instances of inattention or forgetfulness, such as forgetting to signal or check blind spots. The study also found specific sub-criteria within each category, highlighting common behaviors such as overtaking on slow drivers, changing lanes without checking mirrors, and using third gear away from traffic lights. Clear road signage and driver attention were emphasized as important factors in improving behavior.

1. Aggressive violations, such as honking to indicate annoyance and chasing other drivers, were found to pose significant risks on the road, emphasizing the need for measures to address aggressive driving behaviors.
2. Ordinary violations, such as overtaking slow drivers and changing lanes abruptly, were also prevalent among drivers, underscoring the importance of promoting safer driving practices and adherence to traffic regulations.
3. Errors in driver behavior, including failure to use seat belts, underestimating vehicle speeds, and using mobile devices while driving, were identified as areas of concern, highlighting the necessity of enhancing driver education and awareness programs.
4. Lapses in driver behavior, such as incorrect lane approach at roundabout junctions, using inappropriate gears away from traffic lights, and failing to maintain consistent control over vehicle functions, were identified as areas warranting attention, emphasizing the necessity of bolstering driver education and awareness campaigns.

The study offers valuable insights into the factors influencing driver behavior and enhancing traffic management in Peshawar. Fuzzy AHP was employed to rank driver behavior through pairwise comparisons and subsequent analysis of sub-criteria. The utilization of fuzzy AHP yielded significant findings regarding driver behavior assessment.

Limitations

1. Variation in sample sizes and questionnaire scopes across different studies.
2. Reliance on self-reported data, which may introduce biases and inaccuracies.
3. Limited geographical scope in some studies, impacting the generalizability of findings.
4. Potential cultural differences influencing driver behavior, which may not be adequately addressed in cross-cultural studies.

Recommendations

1. Standardization of methodologies and questionnaire designs to ensure consistency and comparability across

studies.

2. Incorporation of objective measures, such as driving simulators or telematics data, in addition to self-reported data, to enhance the reliability of findings.
3. Conducting longitudinal studies to track changes in driver behavior over time and assess the effectiveness of interventions.
4. Collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders to develop targeted interventions and regulations based on research findings.
5. Further exploration of cultural influences on driver behavior to develop culturally sensitive road safety interventions.
6. Utilization of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and big data analytics, to analyze large datasets and identify complex patterns of driver behavior.

By addressing these recommendations, future research can contribute to improving road safety and enhancing transportation systems by better understanding and effectively addressing driver behavior.

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